

PREPARATION OF ULTRA-HIGH MOLECULAR WEIGHT POLYETHYLENE FIBERS, ELECTROSPUN WITH CARBON NANOTUBES

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SUMMARY

Successful preparation of the metastable at the elevated temperatures mutual solutions of ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene and suspension of carbon nanotubes in combination with electrospinning process using the novel device, allowed the manufacturing of nanocomposite micron-sized fibers, reinforced with oriented self-organized nano-ropes from the carbon nanotubes.

Keywords: ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene, carbon nanotubes, nanofiber, electrospinning, nanocomposite

INTRODUCTION

Ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) based gel-spun fibers have great advantages and are used for the different applications [1]. The usage of these fibers in structural composites, however, has been limited by sufficient creep under static conditions and poor shear modulus and strength [2]. Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) are considered to be the perfect reinforcing component for composite materials with exceptional mechanical properties [3]. A large numbers of papers have been published on the reinforcement of different polymer composites using CNTs, but results are mixed. It was specially noted that the most of the CNTs were dispersed in the form of micron-sized roundish clusters and not all the CNTs were aligned with the surrounding matrix [4, 5]. Uniform dispersion within the polymer matrix and improved nanotube-matrix wetting and adhesion are the critical issues in the processing of the CNT based composites and fibers. The extremely high drawing of polymer/CNT melts, solutions or suspensions in the course of the fiber spinning with the goal to manufacture the fibers with near-micron diameters could also assist to the CNT cluster destruction and subsequent orientation of the individual CNT together with surrounding polymer matrix. The best process that could help to realize the aforesaid demands is the polymer melt or solution electrospinning [6, 7].

MATERIALS, METHODS, RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The key problem in the carrying out of the declared ideas is the correct selection of the solvent. The freedom of our choice is limited by the properties of UHMWPE – it

has a restricted amount of organic solvents acceptable for electrospinning process, the most known of which are decalin, tetralin, p-xylene and paraffin oil [6]. On the other hand, the preparation of the CNT solutions has one huge obstacle: owing to their high molecular weight, nanotubes are considered insoluble in all known solvents. In fact, the ideal situation would be to find a solvent in which nanotubes were thermodynamically soluble, that is, where the free energy of mixing is negative. However, the large molecular weight and high rigidity of nanotubes leads to extremely small entropy of mixing. Due to large mutual attraction of nanotubes, enthalpy of mixing is generally expected to be positive for all conceivable solvent–nanotube mixtures, resulting in a positive free energy of mixing, prohibiting nanotube dissolution [8]. So, for example, the successful dispersing of the pristine nanotubes in water usually could be realized only using the third, dispersant phase [9], existence of which for the specific organic solvents is unsearched up to now. Fortunately, a group of organic solvents that allows the preparing of the relatively stable CNT suspensions is discovered in [10]. Analysis of published data has led to the conclusion that the most acceptable potential candidate for the role of the mutual solvent for UHMWPE and CNT is the o-dichlorobenzene (o-DCB). This substance is a poor solvent for UHMWPE [11], it has an acceptable properties for electrospinning process (electroconductivity – $17 \cdot 10^6$ pS/m; dielectric constant – 7.5; boiling temperature – 180°C ; density – $1.3 \cdot 10^3$ kg/m³) and could form a quasi-stable suspensions with CNT [10].

Preparation and stability of CNT suspension

As was marked in [10], the CNT suspension in o-DCB is stable at the room temperature more than 3 days. The problem is that UHMWPE solution in o-DCB could not exist at room temperature. We have to investigate the stability (time before the coagulation) of CNT suspensions at elevated temperatures. In this work we used multi-wall CNT (MWCNT) by Nanolab Ltd., (30 ± 15 nm diameter, length 5-20 μm); single-wall CNT (SWCNT) by Aldrich Ltd. (CarboLex AP-grade, 15-20 Å diameter); o-DCB – by Fluka AG (practical grade). The production materials were used directly, with no purification. As past indication points to the fact that no more than 95 mg/L of CNT can be suspended in o-DCB [10], (50–80 mg/L) CNT suspensions in o-DCB were prepared by sonication (using the sonicator model 1000L by Ultrasonic Power Corp., USA work capacity 100 sonic frequency 25kHz) The sonication process (continuing a in range of 3–15 minutes) was realized after heating the solvent to the in range of 130 – 150°C , subsequent introduction of CNT and preliminary magnetic stirring of mixture for a couple of minutes. The resulting suspensions were stayed in the heating oil bath at the preparation up to their coagulation. It has been found that the best results (i.e. suspension stability at elevated temperature during more than 3 hours) could be obtained using SWCNT suspension with about 60 mg/L, sonication time 5 min, and mixture temperature about 140°C .

Preparation and stability of UHMWPE solution

UHMWPE powder (GUR 415 from Hoechst, $M_w = 6 \times 10^6$ kg/kmol) was dissolved in hot (about 140°C) o-DCB using magnet stirrer. Antioxidant (2,6-Di-tert-butyl-p-cresol by Fluka AG) was added to the solution at 0.02% (w/v) so as to minimize the

chances of polymer oxidation. Dissolution process was realized by adding the specific portions (0.1 wt%) of UHMWPE powder and intense mixture stirring up to full dissolution of this powder in the solvent. The long been known effect of initial rise followed by a drop in the solution viscosity was observed. This usually interpreted as a building up and subsequent breaking down of a gel network [12-14]. As an indicator of the viscosity changes in our work were used the changes in the rotational velocity of the magnet stirrer sunken into the solution ("apparent viscosity"). The increasing of viscosity leads to the decreasing of the stirrer rotational velocity. The maximum in the apparent viscosity always occurred after 50–250 s from the beginning of UHMWPE powder portion dissolution and its presence was found to be a weakly dependent from the initial rotational velocity of the magnet stirrer, value of UHMWPE powder portion (into the investigated range of 0.1–0.25 wt.%) and current value of the UHMWPE solution concentration (into the investigated range of 0.1–3 wt.%). If the stirring process is stopped when the apparent viscosity is reached its maximum value, the solution will form a spinnable gel during cooling. The solution ability to form a spinnable gel ("solution spinnability") is lost after a long-time stirring ("over-stirring") [14]. The solution spinnability could be represented by the formation of the thin fiber that streams out behind the needle, when it is pulled out from the solution. We have found that the spinnable state of solution, being reached, can persist over many hours or several days at temperatures as high as 170 °C, which is in agreement with the early investigations [14].

The new effect, that we have investigated, consists in possibility to temporarily return the spinnability to "over-stirred" solution by way of dissolving in it the additional portions (0.1–0.25 wt.%) of UHMWPE powder. In these tests the solution was stirred after insertion of every additional portion of UHMWPE until the apparent viscosity level dropped. It was marked, that at solution concentrations more than about 0.8 wt.% the apparent viscosity level remained very high after its initial drop and even after the extinction of all solution spinnability. The successive repetition of procedure: "dissolving the portion of polymer – over-stirring of solution" allows reaching the relatively high concentrations of UHMWPE solutions nonetheless possessing the acceptable viscosity and spinnability. Experimentally was found that the optimal viscosity level for the electrospinning process is reached at 140 °C for 0.5 wt% UHMWPE solution in o-DCB. The results of this investigation are shown in Figure 1.

The cause of the discovered effect may be suggested as follows: the turning stirrer could germinate the regions of flow, where the shear rate is sufficiently high to extend portions of UHMWPE molecules. Such extended chain portions may then form crystals on coalescence with other locally extended chain portions nearby. So the molecular junctions formed during shearing could have a quasi-crystalline nature and are more stable than any present in the initial stationary solution. These partially extended-chain associations, could become homogeneously distributed throughout the solution and eventually reach an equilibrium distribution as reflected by the constant apparent viscosity and good spinnability of solution. On the experimental evidence they would be expected to contain a larger degree of entanglement than the solution and to be comparatively stable when the flow field is removed. When solution concentration rises, the apparent viscosity also rises because the amount of build network particles grows and they start to stick one to another. But at the same time the interactions between dissolved molecular associations begins to break and grind up the molecular

Figure 1. Dependence of spinnable period of UHMWPE solutions under stirring from its concentration and temperature: 1 – at 140 °C; 2 – at 170 °C.

network and groups more quickly. After a while the apparent viscosity falls and solution spinnability disappears. Dissolving the additional portions of UHMWPE powder into the low concentration solutions allows the regaining of the molecular association network and rebuilding the solution spinnability. The most evidently this effect appears at the temperatures just above the equilibrium dissolution temperature, because the elevated temperature prevents the creation and growing of the stable molecular associations.

Mutual UHMWPE solution and CNT suspension

Elaboration of the mutual UHMWPE solution and CNT suspension is a complicated task. In our investigation we have discovered, that, even in the best case, the direct dissolution of UHMWPE in the hot CNT/o-DCB suspension, prepared by sonication, induces the phase separation of mixture during a few minutes. The inverted process – adding the pure CNT to the hot UHMWPE solution in o-DCB – results in the instant solution coagulation accompanied with partial capture of CNT bundles by the resulting gel. Subsequent sonication gives the quasi-stable mixture (we name it Sono {UHMWPE+CNT}), but this does not improve the homogeneity of CNT distribution in the mixture. The possible cause of this effect may be explain by the fact that, during

sonication at preparation of CNT suspension, o-DCB decomposes and partially polymerizes on the surface of CNT [15], forming the "coke", predominantly composed from low molecular weight crosslinked polystyrenes ("sonopolymer") [16]. This surface layer sufficiently promotes the stability of CNT/o-DCB suspension (we name it {CNT+sonopolymer}) [15], but existence of the excess admixture of sonopolymer in the liquid o-DCB hinders the formation of stable UHMWPE/CNT/o-DCB mixture. Furthermore, if pure o-DCB is preliminary allowed to polymerize sonochemically, CNTs cannot be dispersed in the decomposed and partially polymerized solvent even by vigorous agitation or heating [15]. The adding into mixture the UHMWPE molecules, which compete with o-DCB molecules in adsorbing onto the CNT surface, reduces the suspension stability. Mutual affinity of CNT and UHMWPE molecules also negatively affects on stability of mixture.

According to [15], the addition into o-DCB a small amounts of alcohols or ketones sufficiently inhibits the solvent decomposition during sonication, which could eliminate the excess admixture of sonopolymer in the liquid o-DCB. This phenomenon facilitates the CNT/UHMWPE mutual interaction. But it is necessary to take into consideration the discovered experimental fact, that addition of ethanol into UHMWPE/CNT/o-DCB mixtures causes its fast coagulation.

The adding of pure UHMWPE into the hot CNT mixture in o-DCB, preliminary sonicated in presence of ethyl alcohol (ethanol, by Fluka AG (96%, practical grade)), results in forming the gel, consists of UHMWPE with practically fully captured CNTs, evenly dispersed into the gel volume. Subsequent sonication gives the quasi-stable mixture (we name it Sono {UHMWPE+CNT+ethanol}) consists of the evenly dispersed UHMWPE/CNT gel scraps into the o-DCB volume.

Results of our investigation are shown in Table 1, where we have attempted to qualitatively rank the relative strength of intermolecular interaction of investigated substances in their mixtures in o-DCB. This rank was estimated as being proportional to the sonic energy, necessary to transfer these substances into the mixture in o-DCB, and being inversely to the stability of these mixtures.

Table 1. Relative strength of the intermolecular interactions of the investigated substances in o-DCB and stability of their mutual mixtures at 140 °C.

Added pure substances	CNT	o-DCB	UHMWPE
Base mixture of o-DCB with:			
pure o-DCB	*↑		**↔
CNT		*↑	***↓
UHMWPE	****↓	**↔	
{CNT+sonopolymer}		**↔	***↑
Sono {UHMWPE+CNT+ethanol }		**↔	**↔

Here: * – relative strength of the intermolecular interactions in o-DCB (proportionally to the number of * signs); ↔ – sign, that the substance remains in the dissolved state

during tens of hours; ⚡ – sign, that the substance coagulate during tens of minutes; ⚡ – sign, that the substance coagulate instantly.

Electrospinning of UHMWPE/CNT mixture in o-DCB

The electrospinning process was realized on the device described in [6, 7] at the process conditions disclosed *ibid*. The intrinsic structure of electrospun fibers, produced from the investigated mixture, consists from the spontaneously formed CNT nano-ropes imbedded into the UHMWPE fibers which could be seen on the scanning electron microscope (SEM) pictures – Figure 2.

Figure 2. SEM pictures of nascent electrospun UHMWPE fibers with CNT nano-ropes.

CONCLUSIONS

Thus, as a generalization of the preliminary experimental investigations, the working protocol for mixture of UHMWPE and SWCNT in o-DCB was set as follows: 60 mg/L of SWCNT is added to the hot (140 °C) o-DCB and mixed together by magnet stirrer during 3 minutes. 1 wt.% of ethanol is added to this mixture and subsequent sonication for 5 minutes yields the relatively stable CNT/o-DCB suspension. 0.25 wt.% of UHMWPE is introduced to the obtained suspension under continuous stirring, which induces the quick polymer dissolution and subsequent coagulation of the dissolved

UHMWPE to gel with CNT, evenly dispersed into it volume. Additional 5 minutes of sonication under heating is applied to evenly disperse the obtained UHMWPE/CNT gel and fully evaporate the ethanol from the hot mixture, which needs to prevent the further UHMWPE solution coagulation. Finally, 0.25 wt.% of UHMWPE is added to mixture for correction of "over-stirring" and attainment of the necessary mixture viscosity and spinnability. The obtained mixture remains stable and spinnable in storage at 140 °C during about 1 hour.

The nano-ropes, formed in UHMWPE fibers during electrospinning, are strongly oriented along the fiber axis and, in our opinion, could be a good reinforcement framework for the following fiber drawing and subsequent utilization in the UHMWPE polymer/CNT fiber based composites.

The discovered technology for preparation of micron-sized UHMWPE fibers, reinforced with CNT nano-ropes, allows the manufacturing of the necessary amount of nano-composite fibers, the physics-mechanical properties of which we are now discovering.

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